

GEOMETRICAL AND DEFORMATION CHARACTERISTICS OF 3-D BRAIDED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Geometrical models of 4-step braided composites (or preforms) have been developed based on preform fabrication process and three-dimensional curved yarns. The geometry is expressed by four micro-structural parameters, which are determined for preforms and composites using yarn jamming conditions and yarn deformation during consolidation, respectively. Next, three-dimensional iso-strain model is developed for the analysis of elastic properties of 4-step braided composites. Experiments are conducted to evaluate the geometrical model and iso-strain model, and the results show good agreement with the prediction.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous models have been developed to represent the architecture of three dimensional braided composites or preforms. Most of the existing models are composed of an assemblage of straight yarn segments [1]. Recently, models which express yarns as three-dimensional curved segments have been proposed [2]. In these curved yarn models, since the yarn cross-section and yarn contact condition are highly idealized, the yarn architectures are far from being realistic, and the fiber volume fractions are limited to low values.

GEOMETRICAL CHARACTERIZATION

CURVED YARN MODEL

In braided preforms and composites, yarns are three-dimensionally curved. For modeling curved yarns, the center line of a yarn is defined by a position vector $\mathbf{R}_c(\tau)$ in the x-y-z coordinate system (Fig. 1), where the z axis coincides with the direction of braiding. Here, we introduce local coordinate system 1-2-3, whose origin lies on the center line. The 1-axis coincides with the tangent vector of the yarn center line, which indicates the fiber longitudinal direction.

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Figure 1. Three-dimensional curved yarn model

The surface of yarn is defined by ellipses which lie in the plane parallel to the x-y plane. The orientation of the major axis (1'-axis) of the ellipse is parallel to the projection of the tangent vector of the center line onto the x-y plane. Thus, the surface of the yarn is expressed by the parameters τ and θ ($0 \leq \theta < 2\pi$) as

$$\mathbf{R}(\tau, \theta) = \mathbf{R}_0(\tau) + \frac{d}{2\sqrt{l^2 + m^2}} \left[\left(f \frac{l}{n} \cos\theta - m \sin\theta \right) \mathbf{i} + \left(f \frac{m}{n} \cos\theta + l \sin\theta \right) \mathbf{j} \right] \quad (1)$$

where l , m , and n are direction cosines of the 1-axis with respect to the x, y and z axes. d and f are yarn thickness and yarn aspect ratio respectively, and they are assumed to be constant throughout the yarn. The length of minor axis of the ellipse is d and the major axis is fd/n .

As to the preforms, it is assumed that yarn cross-sectional shape is elliptical and yarns are in contact with each other. On the other hand, in the composites, the yarn cross-sectional shape is no longer elliptical. By deforming the yarn cross-sectional shape, high yarn volume fraction of the composite can be attained. Instead of deforming the yarn cross-sectional shape, we assume that yarn cross-sectional shape is elliptical and yarns can overlap with each other. In the overlap region the yarn volume is counted twice. When yarn A and yarn B contact with each other at a point, the contact condition can be obtained by the following equations;

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_A(\tau_{A0}, \theta_{A0}) &= \mathbf{R}_B(\tau_{B0}, \theta_{B0}) \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_A(\tau_{A0}, \theta_{A0})}{\partial \theta_A} \times \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_B(\tau_{B0}, \theta_{B0})}{\partial \theta_B} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_A(\tau_{A0}, \theta_{A0})}{\partial \theta_A} \bullet \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_A(\tau_{A0}, \theta_{A0})}{\partial \tau_A} \times \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}_B(\tau_{B0}, \theta_{B0})}{\partial \tau_B} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the subscripts A, B and 0 denote the yarn A, yarn B, and the contact point, respectively. Operators \times and \bullet denote cross product and dot product.

GEOMETRY OF 4-STEP BRAIDED PREFORMS AND COMPOSITES

As an example for representing braided composites (or preforms) by the mathematical models, we use the 4-step braided composite with an 8×4 carrier array. Figure 2 shows the projection of yarn center lines onto the braiding bed of the preform whose width is W and thickness is T .

Figure 2. Projection of center lines onto the braiding bed of preforms

Here, the x-y plane coincides with the braiding bed and the z axis is in the braiding direction. The distance advanced by the braid in the z direction in one machine cycle (four steps) is termed as the pitch length h . As shown in Fig. 2, yarns are divided into three kinds of segments, inner straight yarn, surface curved yarn and corner curved yarn, by the geometry of their center lines. The straight yarn segments intersect at the angle 2β on the plane of projection. The distance between the center lines of the straight yarn segment is taken to be the yarn thickness d . There are sixteen surface yarn segments and four corner yarn segments.

The geometry for each yarn segment is expressed using micro-structural parameters of pitch length h , yarn thickness d , yarn intersecting angle β , and yarn aspect ratio f as [3]

$$\mathbf{R} = dG_1\left(\frac{h}{d}, \beta, f, \tau, \theta\right)\mathbf{i} + dG_2\left(\frac{h}{d}, \beta, f, \tau, \theta\right)\mathbf{j} + hG_3(\beta, \tau, \theta)\mathbf{k} \quad (3)$$

where G_1 , G_2 , and G_3 are functions of normalized pitch length h/d , β , f , τ and θ . h is determined by take up speed of preforms (mm/4 steps) and it can be obtained by direct measurement of the composite (or preform). From Fig. 2, the width W and thickness T of the composite (or preform) are expressed by

$$W = d(7/\sin \beta + 2) \quad (4)$$

$$T = d(3/\cos \beta + 2) \quad (5)$$

Thus, d and β are obtained by measuring W and T of composites. d is also expressed by

$$d = \sqrt{\frac{4\lambda}{\pi\rho\kappa f}} \quad (6)$$

where λ , ρ and κ are yarn liner density, fiber density and yarn packing fraction, respectively. Thus, if κ is predicted, f can be obtained. The determination of κ and f is demonstrated later. Once these parameter are obtained, yarn volume fraction V_y and fiber volume fraction V_f are also obtained. Figure 3 shows the geometry of composite (or preform) for one pitch length, where $h/d = 6$, $\beta = 45^\circ$ and $f = 1.5$.

Figure 3. Geometry of 4-step braided composite with one pitch length

MICRO-STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATION

Yarn Contact Condition

The yarn contact condition is used to determine the preform structure. Since the straight yarn segments occupy more than half of the total yarn volume, the contact condition for straight yarns is determined to characterize the preform structure. Substituting the expression of yarn geometry (Eqn (3)) into Eqn (2), the relation among h/d , β , and f for contact of straight yarns is calculated numerically and expressed in the following general

$$f = G_4\left(\frac{h}{d}, \beta\right) \quad (7)$$

where G_4 is a function of h/d and β . Figure 4 shows the relation of Eqn (7) for $\beta = 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ and 60° . At $\beta = 45^\circ$, f is maximum. f assumes the same value for β and $\pi/2 - \beta$. In the region above each curve, the yarns overlap with each other. In the region below each curve, preforms becomes unstable due to lack of support between yarns.

Yarn Jamming Conditions

As to 4-step braided preforms, the following conditions are assumed in the derivation of yarn jamming conditions: (1) straight yarns throughout the preform structure contact with each other, (2) yarns are in a stable configuration in the jamming state, and (3) yarn packing fraction assumes its maximum value κ_{max} in the jamming state. When yarns contact each other, the length of straight yarn segment L_3 for one pitch length is given in the following form

$$L_3 / \sqrt{\frac{4\lambda}{\pi\rho\kappa_{max}}} = G_5\left(\frac{h}{d}, \beta\right) \quad (8)$$

where G_5 is a function of h/d and β . The left-hand side of Eqn (8) is the straight yarn length normalized by a constant. Figure 5 shows the normalized straight yarn length as a function of

Figure 4. Yarn contact condition

Figure 5. Relation between normalized pitch length and normalized straight yarn length

normalized pitch length for $\beta = 30^\circ$ and 45° . Here it is assumed that when two different preforms have the same normalized straight yarn length, the two structures can interchange. In Fig. 5, for a given normalized straight yarn length there exist different normalized pitch lengths. When the normalized straight yarn length is minimum, the preform has only one normalized pitch length and it is in the jamming state. From the geometrical relation, angle θ_z between the z-axis (braiding direction) and the 1-axis (fiber longitudinal direction) is given by

$$\tan \theta_z = 4d / (h \sin 2\beta) \quad (9)$$

At jamming state, $h/d = 2.8$ and $f = 1$. Substituting $\beta = 45^\circ$, $f = 1$, κ_{max} and yarn properties (λ , ρ) into Eqns. (4), (5), and (6), yarn thickness d and pitch length h at the jamming state are obtained.

Micro-structural Parameters for Preforms and Composites

When preforms are not in jamming state, they can assume various pitch lengths. Thus, h must be obtained by measuring the preforms. When preforms are under tensile loading, $\beta = 45^\circ$. Here, we assume that d is identical to that of the jamming state. Then, f is obtained by substituting h/d into Eqn (7). κ is obtained using Eqn (6).

After the preform is consolidated, dimensions of the composite depend on the dimensions of the mold used. Thus, d and β of a composite are obtained from Eqns (4) and (5) using measured W and T values. In the model for composite, yarns are assumed to overlap with each other. When a yarn is compacted during consolidation, the yarn packing fraction increases from the κ_0 to κ , where κ_0 is the yarn packing fraction of the preform before consolidation. Then, force equilibrium for the yarn is expressed by

$$P_y = k_y (\kappa - \kappa_0) \quad (10)$$

where P_y is the pressure acting on the yarn and k_y is an equivalent spring constant of the yarn. During consolidation, yarn volume fraction also increases from V_{y0} to V_y , where V_{y0} is the yarn

volume fraction of the preform before consolidation. The force equilibrium at the preform level is

$$P_p = k_p (V_y - V_{y0}) \quad (11)$$

where P_p is the pressure acting on the preform and k_p is an equivalent spring constant of the preform. Assuming $P_y = P_p$ and $k_y = k_p$, and using the relation $V_f = \kappa V_y$, κ is obtained;

$$\kappa = -\frac{1}{2} \left[V_{y0} - \kappa_0 - \sqrt{(V_{y0} - \kappa_0)^2 + 4V_f} \right] \quad (12)$$

V_y and κ have the maximum values of 1 and κ_{max} , respectively. Hence, when V_y or κ reaches its maximum value, 1 or κ_{max} , the other value is obtained by using $V_f = \kappa V_y$. When both of κ and V_y reach to their maximum values, the composite can not be compacted further. Once κ is obtained, f of the composite is also obtained by Eqn (6). Thus, the required quantities (h , d , β , f) for a 4-step braided composite can be obtained from the measured W , T and h values of the composite and material properties of yarns (ρ and λ).

In Fig. 6, V_f , V_y , and κ are plotted as functions of h and T for 4-step braided composites fabricated by 3K E-glass 3K. κ_{max} is assumed to be 0.8 as demonstrated later in experiments. It is also assumed that W is the same as that of the preform, and h and T are varied from the jamming state (C). In region A, $V_y = 1$ and $\kappa = V_f$. In region B, $\kappa = 0.8$ and $V_y = V_f/0.8$.

Figure 6. Fiber volume fraction V_f , yarn volume fraction V_y , and yarn packing fraction κ of 3K E-glass composite

ELASTIC PROPERTIES

Assuming the iso-strain condition over the composite, the effective stiffness of the composite is obtained by stiffness averaging method. Figure 7 shows the effective Young's modulus \bar{E}_{zz} of 4-step braided composites of E-glass 3K yarn and epoxy system. \bar{E}_{zz} is calculated based upon

Figure 7. Effective Young's modulus \bar{E}_{zz} of E-glass 3K/epoxy composite

the condition shown in Fig. 6. The results show that \bar{E}_{zz} is more sensitive to T than h when the width W of the composite is fixed.

EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

In order to evaluate the geometrical model, 4-step braided composite specimens (E-glass 3K/vinyl ester) were prepared (Table 1). There are three different types of specimens with large (L), medium (M), and small (S) pitch lengths. For specimens of medium pitch length, the thickness of specimens was varied (M-1 - M-5). Fiber volume fraction V_f and yarn packing fraction κ were measured and compared with predicted values. Yarn packing fractions were obtained by image analysis. Table 1 shows good agreement between experiments and predictions.

For specimens S, M-2, M-3, and L, tensile tests were conducted to evaluate the effective Young's modulus \bar{E}_{zz} (Table 2). Predicted Young's moduli are in good agreement with experiments.

Table 1. Experimental evaluation of geometrical model

Specimen ID	Width, mm	Thickness, mm	Pitch length, mm	Fiber volume fraction, %		Yarn packing fraction, %	
				Experiment	Prediction	Experiment	Prediction
S	12.5	4.24	4.46	39.9	40.1	55.0	55.2
M-1	12.4	5.22	7.54	30.5	30.2	43.7	42.9
M-2	12.4	4.07	6.80	38.2	38.7	50.5	50.5
M-3	12.6	3.28	6.96	49.2	47.0	55.4	56.5
M-4	12.7	2.38	7.50	64.1	63.7	66.5	67.3
M-5	13.1	1.85	7.15	80.0	80.2	80.0	80.2
L	12.4	4.04	11.02	37.1	37.3	47.4	47.4

Table 2. Experimental evaluation of Young's modulus

Specimen I.D.	Young's modulus, GPa	
	Experiment	\bar{E}_{∞}
S	16.7	18.6
M-2	22.9	23.0
M-3	28.1	27.8
L	26.7	26.6

CONCLUSIONS

The theoretical and experimental studies performed on 4-step braided composites have established the inter-relationship among preform fabrication, micro-mechanics, and elastic property. The knowledge so established will benefit the design of structural component based upon 4-step braiding technology.

REFERENCES

1. T. W. Chou, Microstructural design of fiber composites, Cambridge University Press (1992).
2. A. Abusfieh, S. R. Kalidindi, and E. Franco, An experimental and numerical study of response of 3-D braided structural textile composites. *Proc. 9th ASC*, 1118-1125 (1994).
3. M. Ito, Effects of yarn undulation on the stress and deformation of textile composites. *Ph. D. Dissertation. University of Delaware*, (1995).